

Enhancing Good Governance in Madhesh: Madhesh University's Role

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Abstract

Madhesh University, as a key higher education institution in the region, plays a vital role in advancing good governance through transparency, accountability, and citizen participation. This study explores how Madhesh University's academic programs, community outreach, and research promote openness and ethical leadership in public administration through the "Madhesh Governance Forum" and "Federalism Dialogue Series" foster collaboration between academia and policymakers, resulting in digital tools that improve accountability in public service delivery. Madhesh Province faces unique socio-political challenges, making strong enforcement of the Madhesh Province Education Policy 2081 urgent. To support this, establishing an integrated Service Commission and skill schools, and focusing on employment generation are essential steps. The university's efforts contribute directly to building a better Madhesh by addressing regional disparities and bureaucratic opacity along with promoting tree planting as a graduation requirement for making responsible citizens. The patent registration and continuous publication resulted to be ranked as one of the top university of Nepal. out of 64 institutions in Nepal evaluated by AD Scientific Index, Madhesh University stands notably in the middle national tier as 22nd position but is a leading institution in the Madhesh region need to open technical courses along with hulkali national highway to draw foreign students here as well. Recommendations urge expanding university-government partnerships to integrate ethical leadership into civil service training, promoting sustainable development and prosperity.

Keyword: good governance, transparency, accountability, prosperity, citizen's engagement, robust governance, sustainable development